

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B027
 Date: 07 Jul 2004
 Take Off 11:43:35
 Landing: 14:17:35
 Flight Time 2h34m00

Trials Instructions: Pre-ITOP – Informal Intercomparison Flight with DLR Falcon.
Operating Area: N Sea (Norwich/Wittering)

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	Pilot	Charlie Wittaker	BAe Systems
4	Mission Scientist 1	Dave Kindred	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
6	Flight Manager (training)	John Reid	FAAM
7	Core Chemistry/FWVS/CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
8	PTR-MS	Anne Hulse	UEA
9	ORAC / PAN	Lisa Whalley	Leeds University
10	PERCA	Alex Parker	Leicester University
11	AMS	Paul Williams	UMIST
12	Observer	Hans Schleger	DLR
13	Mission Scientist 2	Ally Lewis	York University
14	Observer / HORACE	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office
15	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
16			
17			
18			

Flight Track:

B027 Track 07-JUL-04

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B027
 Date: 07/07/2004
 Project: Pre-ITOP Intercomparison with DLR Falcon
 Location: Cranfield

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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112435					INU to Nav
113750					Taxy
114335		T/O	0.00 kft		Cranfield
115015	120016	Run 1	10.0 kft	016	
122030	122750	Run 2.1	10.0 kft	112	
123456	124233	Run 2.2	10.0 kft	283	
124233	125230	Profile 1	10.0 - 15.0 kft		spiral ascent
125342	130121	Run 3.1	15.0 kft	106	
130514	131244	Run 3.2	15.0 kft	287	
131215					HORACE crash
131244	131845	Profile 2	15.0 - 20.0 kft		
132419	133151	Run 4.1	20.0 kft	099	
133613	134350	Run 4.2	20.0 kft	281	
134350					end formation flying
141735		Land	0.00 kft	270	Cranfield
142810		GPS final position 52.04.36N 00 37.50W			

B027 Track 07-JUL-04

B027: Pre-ITOP – Informal Intercomparison Flight with DLR Falcon.

Mission Scientist: Ally Lewis/Dave Kindred

Date: 07/07/04

Outline schedule:

- 07:30 - Power to aircraft – Warm-up**
- 10:00 - D-CMET arrives**
- 10:30 - 146/Falcon Air Crew face-to-face Briefing**
- 11:30 - Science brief for all flyers (146 and Falcon)**
- 13:15 - Wet chemistry checks (all aboard)**
- 13.30 - Take-off of G-LUXE**
- 13.45 - Take-off of D-CMET**

Location: North Sea (Norwich/Wittering)

Alternative location in case of cloud: Bristol Channel / SW approaches.

Aim

The aim of this sortie is to test the ITOP instruments against another platform, the DLR Falcon Aircraft. It will provide an invaluable dataset for the acceptance in addition to other intercomparison missions planned. The intercomparison will take place in a box (52deg40mins North, 1deg 17min East) and Wittering (52deg 37min North, 0deg 28min West) at FL100 and above. Runs are of a length sufficient for the chemistry instruments to perform calibrations at each level. All profiles at 1000 ft/min unless otherwise indicated. The Falcon will return to Cranfield for refuelling after the intercomparison before returning to Oberpfaffenhofen. Additional time is given for the profiles to allow realignment of aircraft.

Sortie Detail

1. T+0 Take Off.
2. Transit towards operating area. Transit should include at least 20 mins at constant altitude (FL100 or similar) for calibration purposes. (30)
3. T +30 Positioning at FL100 (10)
4. T +40 Rendezvous with Falcon aircraft. Race-track level run 15 minutes FL100. Wingtip formation. (15)
5. T +55 Profile ascent and repositioning to FL150 (7)
6. T +62 Race track level run 15 minutes FL150. Wingtip formation. (15)
7. T +77 Profile ascent and repositioning to FL200 (7)
8. T +84 Race track level run 15 minutes FL200. Wingtip formation. (15)
9. T +99 Profile ascent and repositioning to FL250 (7)
10. T +106 Race track level run 15 minutes FL250. Wingtip formation. (15)
11. T +121 Profile descent to FL100 (15)
12. T +136 Transit to Cambridge to include at least 20mins at constant altitude at FL100 for calibration purposes (30)
13. T+ 166 Land Cranfield.

B027: Pre-ITOP – Informal Intercomparison Flight with DLR Falcon.

Mission Scientist: Ally Lewis/Dave Kindred

Date: 07/07/04

T₀ 1145

L 1420

Outline schedule:

- 07:30 - Power to aircraft – Warm-up
- 10:00 - D-CMET arrives
- 10:30 - 146/Falcon Air Crew face-to-face Briefing
- 11:00 ~~11:30~~ - Science brief for all flyers (146 and Falcon)
- 13:15 - Wet chemistry checks (all aboard)
- 1230 ~~13:30~~ - Take-off of G-LUXE
- 13.45 - Take-off of D-CMET

T. 2h35m

15 POB

Land by 1530L

Location: North Sea (Norwich/Wittering)

Alternative location in case of cloud: Bristol Channel / SW approaches.

Aim

The aim of this sortie is to test the ITOP instruments against another platform, the DLR Falcon Aircraft. It will provide an invaluable dataset for the acceptance in addition to other intercomparison missions planned. The intercomparison will take place in a box (52deg40mins North, 1deg 17min East) and Wittering (52deg 37min North, 0deg 28min West) at ~~FL100~~ and above. Runs are of a length sufficient for the chemistry instruments to perform calibrations at each level. All profiles at 1000 ft/min unless otherwise indicated. The Falcon will return to Cranfield for refuelling after the intercomparison before returning to Oberpfaffenhofen. Additional time is given for the profiles to allow realignment of aircraft.

FL050

check Horace chem paras against instruments on Mission Net.

Sortie Detail

1. T+0 Take Off.
2. Transit towards operating area. Transit should include at least 20 mins at constant altitude (FL100 or similar) for calibration purposes. (30) *210kts*
3. T +30 Positioning at FL100 (10)
4. T +40 Rendezvous with Falcon aircraft. Race-track level run 15 minutes FL100. Wingtip formation. (15)
5. T +55 Profile ascent and repositioning to FL150 (7) *log Falcon time*
6. T +62 Race track level run 15 minutes FL150. Wingtip formation. (15) *in e two turns*
7. T +77 Profile ascent and repositioning to FL200 (7)
8. T +84 Race track level run 15 minutes FL200. Wingtip formation. (15)
9. T +99 Profile ascent and repositioning to FL250 (7)
10. T +106 Race track level run 15 minutes FL250. Wingtip formation. (15)
11. T +121 Profile descent to FL100 (15)
12. T +136 Transit to ~~Cambridge~~ ^{Cranfield} to include at least 20mins at constant altitude at FL100 for calibration purposes (30)
13. T+ 166 Land Cranfield.

AMS key

Mission Scientist's Log

ACL.

Flight No **B.027**.....

Date **7/7/04**.....

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TR
Aerosol
ORAC
WAS
PAN
CO
O3
NO
LAS

UT GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:43:40					T/O
					Cloud base broken 6000ft
		10000			Cal Run 210 kts
115500	1-1 cal checks				CO 70/77 O3 50/51
120016	end Run				1/2 S 7/8 cirrus
		8000			Thinner to North
		8000			PTC, ✓ Aerosol, AMS ^x CPC,
		8000			ORAC, WAS, PAN,
120800		8000			clear below over sea,
					6/9 cirrus.
121200		8000			LH orbit
122020	2-0	10000	090		First Run
123100		FL100		210 kts	WAS fill
122709		FL100		200 kts	105 117 windspeed/dir.
122748	2-1	10000			End of Run
122946					LH Turn
123456	2-2	FL100			Return Run.
124233					end of Run
					LH
124233	profile 1				Climb to FL150
					clear below 5/8 cirrus

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Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B...027**

 Date **7/7/04**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	3-1	FL150	200pts		clear above + below.
			-20		
125400		FL150	205pts		056 / 15
130600		FL150			was fill 2 bottles.
130121	3-1	"			end of run.
130514	3-2	FL150			
					O ₃ spot, 86 ppb Falcon
	HORACE Gashed.				83 ppb.
131000		FL150			clear above + below.
	4.1	FL200			Run started ↓ also
132409		FL200			
133700		FL200			canister fill
1331 133151					LH turn.
133600	4.2	FL200			start of run.
133854					Spot CO 98 Falcon
					(95) ← -105 146 (+10 offset)
134000		FL200			224 / 13 winds
134352		FL200			end of run

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

Flight No B.027.....

Date 07/07/04.....

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Video Tapes		GPS	INU	DRS <input type="checkbox"/>
V8		Lat	52° 04.36'N	52° 04.38'N
No ① 15:50		Long	0° 37.25'W	0° 37.25'W
Ends		Time	11:12:03	11:12:46
FFC / RFC / DFC / UFC		Status	✓	GC align
				HORACE <input type="checkbox"/>
				SATCOM <input type="checkbox"/>

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/Sea st.
112435		INU to	Navigate					
113158		Engine	Start					
113750		Taxi	start					
114335		Take off	from Cranfield					
F		Start of	Run 1 (S&L Cal run)					
115015	3	FL100		016				
120016	4	end of	Run 1					
120620	5	Recycled	DFC title to remove 'MODE1' message on display.					
		Start of	Run 2.1	Comparison with D-CMET.				
122030	No EM	FL100		112				
122750	6	end of	Run 2.1					
		Start of	Run 2.2					
123456	7	FL100		283				
124233	8	end of	Run 2.2					
		Start of	Profile 1					
124233	8	FL100			↗	to FL150	(Spiral)	
125230						end of	Profile 1	

B027
T/O Cranfield

7/7/04
114333

1/8 Cw & 7/8 Ci/Cs above

+
Falcon +
146

~ 12.20.30 Start Run 2.1

Hdg 111 deg Speed 242 ktr Hr 9.9 ktr

1/8 Ci/Cs
above
(thicker to SW)
(fainter to NE)

53.4 N
1.4 E

Wind 093/7 m/sec⁻¹

TAS 202 ktr

Cw below
over sea

1227 30

Wind 105/8 m/sec⁻¹

2/8 Cw over land

12.27.50

End Run 2.1

FL 100

53.2° N
2.0° E

1230 Turning

123456

Start Run 2.2

FL 100

53.3° N
1.8° E

Wind 104°/7 m/sec⁻¹

Hdg 283 deg TAS

1237

Bottle filled

1242

End Run 2.2

FL 100

53.4° N
1.0° E

Ascent to FL 150, turning ↗

125230

Profile end P1 at FL 150

125342

Start Run 3.1

at FL 150

53.3 N
1.2° E

4/8 Ci/Cs above

Hdg 107°

T.A. Speed 264 ktr

Flight Deck 057°/16 ktr

1/8 Cw (total)
below

Temp -8.8°C

Helix 4156°/8 m/sec } ✓

1306

Fill 2 bottles consecutively

1258 RFE screen misted

Temp -9°C

DP - 42°C

130121

End Run 3.1

53.1 N

FL 150 2.1° E

130514

Start Run 3.2
FL 150

Hdg 281° TA Speed 276 kt
53.3°N 1.9°E

Wind 144° / 5 m/sec

Temp -8.8°C ; DP = -42.4°C

1312

End Run 3.2

↓ Helix Cashed!

Reboot

Change ^{over} disk

1327

On

Run ~~3.2~~ 4.1

Hdg 110° TAS 287 kt

HT FL 200 53.2°N 1.8°E

Wind 192° / 10 m/sec

Temp -18.1°C ; D. Pt -36.8°C

133151

End Run 4.1

Slip out of formation temporarily (pass and sandwich)

1/8 C below

5/8 Ci / Cs above

(y. thin)

133613

Start Run 4.2 FL 200

Hdg 279° TA Speed 290 kt

53.4°N 1.9°E Wind 206° / 10 m/sec

Temp -18.1°C DP = -39.3°C

Wind 224° / 13 kt FLIGHT DECK

" 201° / 10 m/sec → Helix

134350

End Run 4.2 FL 200

FL 250 w/c cloud, so RTB to land before 1530 L

Flight Manager's Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B027

Instruments

Amty display + lights w/s.

New. TW hand wire loose. w/s

No TWC data on DRS - unit on but source off.
heaters will be operated in flight.

TWC - status light remains 'ON' even after source is switched on and EVAP2 is switched off. ~~So source~~

TWC - status light 'out' with EVAP1 on only
and with both EVAPS on

Horace crash #1 @ 131215 rebooted off. dka100.

Aircraft